

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N. COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number ⑥-⑥a ⑥b

Progress of Excavation R16A1 29/I/80: ⑤ in R16A1, only mm. thin

patches adhering to surface of ⑥. ⑥ Compact finely disintegrated

granite dust ③ Scrapped off Then ⑥ removed to E Balk

w/ trowel // 4/II/80 R16A2 ⑥b CLAY-GYPSUM mix, buff, soft,

w lime, limestone chips (vertically) adhering to face of bedrock foundation ledge.

Looks very similar to ④a-④b. Section at E balk base only removed.

NOTE: IN Beginning to clear ⑥b there showed a subtle separation line between more buff lighter more concentrated gypsum adhering to ledge face and more sandy-clay like, darker brown deposit on floor. This line added →

Locus Description ⑤ BUFF WHITE GYPSUM

⑥ BLUE granite dust in gypsum matrix?

⑥a BUFF WHITE GYPSUM

⑥b BUFF GYPSUM-CLAY

Location in Square See Plan

Under Locus _____ Over Locus _____ →

Locus Dimensions See Plan

Levels SURFACE 7.80 - 7.73

Analysis of non-artifactual materials ⑥: Inclusions: middling sized granite frags, dalerite chips middling sized to very small. Small to middling limestone frags. Some pockets or veins of sand.

⑥b - Large charcoal spot embedded.

⑤
⑥
⑥a

to plan and the 2 deposits cleared separately. The darker, brown
sandy deposit on floor designated (4f)